

Structural, Phase Transition Temperature and Tensile Behavior of PMMA/ZnO Nanocomposite

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Abstract

The nanocomposite of PMMA/ZnO was prepared by solution casting technique by dispersing ZnO nano particles at 4wt% of PMMA content. Dispersion of ZnO nanoparticles alters the structure of pure PMMA which is attributed through Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Phase transition temperature, Young modulus, tensile strength, toughness and fracture strain are analyzed through stress strain curve ascertain through Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA). The study reveals that dispersion of nano ZnO expressively reformed the properties of pure PMMA.

Keywords

Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer, Young Modulus, Tensile Properties, Tensile Strength, Toughness, Fracture Strain

Introduction

Recently, anomalous research has been focused on the development of polymer/ZnO nanocomposite materials using different polymer systems [1-3].

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The nano-sized zinc oxide (ZnO) has fascinated great attention as one of the multifunctional inorganic nanoparticle which offers some significant properties, such as high chemical stability, low dielectric constant, large electromechanical coupling coefficient, intensive ultraviolet and infrared adsorption [4-8]. Consequently, polymer/ZnO nanocomposites can be used in numerous fields such as UV-shielding, photocatalysis, field emission display, gas sensing, and thermoelectricity. Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) is well known industrial thermoplastic polymeric material. A lot of study has been done regarding preparation and characterization of PMMA/nanofiller nanocomposites as PMMA/Clay, PMMA/CdS, PMMA/SAN, PMMA/CNT and etc. [9-11].

The present paper we have discussed about synthesis, structural characterization and tensile properties of PMMA/ZnO nanocomposite. It shows that introduction of dispersed nano ZnO expressively improved the properties of pure PMMA.

Experimental

Material Preparation

The ZnO nanoparticles (particle size 20 nm), PMMA ($M_w = 43,000$) and solvent Tetrahydrofuran (THF) (99.9% purity) of research grade were purchased through sigma Aldrich. Now for the preparation of PMMA/ZnO nanocomposite, PMMA is dissolved in THF solvent, stirred for 24 hrs and then ZnO nanoparticles (4 wt% of PMMA) were dispersed in this solution while continuing stirring for another 24 hrs. After the sufficient hours stirring, the whole solution is poured off into flat-bottomed petri dish and allows the solvent to evaporate slowly over next 24 hours through dry atmosphere. The so found film was then peeled off and dried out in vacuum at 50°C, for next 48 hours [12].

Measurement Techniques

Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (TRITEC-2000 DMA) is a sensitive technique that characterizes the mechanical response of materials by monitoring property change with respect to the temperature and frequency of applied sinusoidal stress. The storage modulus E' , loss modulus E'' and mechanical loss factor ($\tan \delta$) have been determined during the test as a function of increasing temperature.[13,14].

Morphological Characterization

The surface morphology of the samples has been characterized by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) using a SEM (Quanta Fe-200 model).

Figure: 1 (a) SEM micrographs of PMMA and (b) PMMA/ZnO

Fig. 1 (a) and (b) shows the micrographs of pure PMMA and ZnO dispersed PMMA. From the figures it is observed that dispersed nano ZnO filler particle change the morphology of the pure PMMA samples. The SEM images of the pure PMMA shows a porous and granular structure while the ZnO dispersed PMMA matrix exhibits a smoother and more compacted amorphous surface morphology.

Results and Discussion

Phase Transition Temperature Study

The temperature below which a polymer is hard and above which it is soft is called phase transition temperature (T_g) [16]. Fig. 2 shows the $\tan \delta$ with temperature for all of the nanocomposites from room temperature to 110°C. It is observed that on dispersing ZnO in PMMA matrix its $\tan \delta$ peak slight shifts toward higher temperature compared with the pure PMMA. The T_g of pure PMMA is observed at 61.17 OC whereas for its ZnO nanocomposites, it is observed at 64.39 OC.

Figure: 2 Variation of Tan Delta of Pure PMMA & PMMA/ZnO with temperature

Tensile Study

The tensile properties of ZnO/PMMA nanocomposites have been determined through stress-strain measurements in tension mode. Fig 3 shows the stress-strain curves for Pure PMMA and PMMA/ZnO nanocomposites respectively at room temperature. All the mechanical properties such as Young's modulus, ultimate strength, toughness and fracture strain obtained from stress-strain relation have been summarized in Table 1. It is observed that tensile properties show higher value for PMMA/ZnO nanocomposites than that of pure PMMA. The results obtained from the study are explained on the basis of interaction between ZnO nanoparticles and polymer matrix.

Table 1: The results of Mechanical characterization of Pure PMMA & PMMA/ZnO samples

Sample	PMMA	PMMA+ ZnO (4 Wt %)
Young Modulus (MPa)	34.79	78.76
Ultimate Strength (MPa)	2.15	4.92
Toughness (KJ)	73.17	152.61
Fracture Strain (%)	0.543	0.515

Figure: 3 Stress-Strain behavior of Pure PMMA & PMMA/ZnO

The improvement in the mechanical properties is attributed to the interaction between nanoparticles and polymer matrix [17-18]. The nanoparticles have high surface area compared to the conventional fillers and have good interfacial adhesion with the polymer chains so that the mobility of polymer chains is restricted under loading., which increases Young's modulus [19-20] .

Conclusion

We have described a simple route to obtain high quality PMMA/ZnO nanocomposite. The following conclusions can be drawn from the above study:

1. The SEM studies reveal that ZnO nanoparticles embedded in PMMA shows the uniform distribution at 4 Wt% filler percentage.
2. The Phase transition temperature of PMMA/ZnO nanocomposites is found to be increased as compared to pure PMMA.
3. Tensile properties of PMMA/ZnO nanocomposites improve as compared to pure PMMA which is due to overall good interaction between ZnO nanoparticles and PMMA matrix.

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